

STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE PEDAGOGICAL DIRECTION

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Annotation: One of the branches of general pedagogical science is the history of pedagogy. It requires a comprehensive study of the concepts of upbringing, spirituality and enlightenment, changes in pedagogical science in connection with the development of society, the provision of spirituality and enlightenment of a person in every social system.

Key words: pedagogy, history of pedagogy, development of pedagogical ideas, education, Law "About Education", "National Program for Personnel Training".

The methodological basis of the history of the pedagogical direction and the science that perfectly studies the systems of teaching and education in the traditions of educating the younger generation, their rules of law, the ideas of training, enlightenment of encyclopedic thinkers, enlightened poets and educators, and their development. While the science of the history of pedagogy is studying the development of pedagogical ideas in Uzbekistan in the country of Universal, including Turan, Movarounnahr, Turkestan and during the years of independence, this science is aimed at mastering the pedagogical works left by famous and advanced educators in the past and the national foundations of pedagogical theories put forward in them, and After all, in-depth analysis of the teachings, ideas of encyclopedic thinkers, enlightenment poets and advanced educators on the upbringing of young people as a harmonious person, issues of education in schools and madrasas, drawing clear conclusions from them will expand students' independent thinking.

Hence, the history of pedagogy, as an independent branch of pedagogy, approaches historical and pedagogical phenomena on the basis of the demand of the era, showing the variety of theory and practice of education at different stages and the path of development of advanced pedagogical views.

In the current period of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a new approach is being made on the basis of modern concepts in the pedagogical study of historical phenomena in order to scientifically-theoretically objective truthful coverage of the history of the development of pedagogical thought. The coverage of the history of the development of education and education, that is, pedagogical thoughts in Uzbekistan as a holistic development process, in connection with the pedagogical and historical development of the peoples of the world, on a chronological principle, is one of such approaches.

Currently, the Republic is undergoing political, economic, educational and educational-cultural reforms. New principles of humanization of social structures, laws of the attitude of the market economy, changes in ideological and moral principles lead to aggravation of social problems such as unemployment, material shortages, lack of control of children, separation of families, absent social workers-alcoholism, drug addiction, crime, prostitution. In this case, first of all, children, and then adults, are in love with social assistance. In such conditions, a

demand arises for a social educator as a specialist who solves pedagogical issues that depend on the social problems of society, assisting a person in the process of its socialization.

The need for social pedagogy was required by the following circumstances:

First of all, today it is required to identify the reasons for the contradiction between the purpose of education and training and some of its results, and to identify ways to eliminate them. This requirement aroused the need to bring into the world of pedagogy sociology, which deals with relations in society. Because human activity, having a conscious nature, constitutes a specific object of the science of sociology. The understanding of each person's place in society, his own self, the embodiment of life-moral norms, the manifestation of these spiritual and moral qualities in society, the cooperation of the disciplines of pedagogy and sociology in the upbringing of young people in harmony with our social life, our time, plays a special role. Although education is a social phenomenon and a pedagogical process.

Secondly, it requires a new methodology based on the coherence of pedagogical and sociological concepts in order to find solutions to new problems, such as determining the causal nature of the social origin of the spiritual emptiness in the minds of some members of society, creating a mechanism for solving them. When forming a human personality, it is necessary to take into account the natural (hereditary) and social characteristics in it, the possibilities of its higher nervous activity. It is necessary to organize its upbringing on the basis of knowledge of the laws of self-education, adaptation to conditions, orientation to a certain object on the basis of the biological and subjective (personal aspects) of the human body. Opportunities of internal and external influence in the process of personality formation based on such important features as mutual understanding, features of youth activity of the educational process, awareness of the essence, freedom and pride of the individual, relying on Democratic, humanitarian and national principles, the formation of spiritual and moral qualities in them is a period requirement. The transformation of the consciousness, thinking of people into society in a positive way is associated with socio - educational processes. It is important to study it scientifically. The problems caused by the involvement of pedagogy and sociology also attract the close attention of scientists from Uzbekistan.

Also, the issue of the construction and structure of the educational subject of the history of pedagogy is very important, since the logic and nature of the statement of pedagogical-historical phenomena, ideas, theories, views can facilitate or complicate the assimilation of this subject by students. In our opinion, it is advisable to state the study of the history of pedagogy in Uzbekistan in the form of a single, universal (world) pedagogical thought development process in connection with the development of pedagogical theories, ideas, thoughts of the peoples of the world. In this approach, based on the periodization of the history of Uzbekistan and the history of Uzbek pedagogy, the development of pedagogical ideas at each stage, period in ancient Turan, Movarounnahr, Turkestan and independent Uzbekistan, as well as in other regions of the world is described. This makes the history of pedagogy easy for students to master.

In order to cover the science of the history of pedagogy as a holistic, single cultural and educational, pedagogical historical process, it is necessary to abandon the statement of another creed that is firmly established in our minds by linking historical materials on education with social structures and formations. The complex thing about this approach is that the socio-economic development of different countries in the world will not be the same,

but will be different. At the same time, one should not forget that such an approach is still based on the belief that the economic base plays a decisive role in the development of society.

Individuals who have lost hope in life, do not believe in themselves, are unable to independently solve life problems, expect human help, understanding, companion attachment to his grief. Instilling self-confidence in such individuals with their word and activity, helping them to realize their capabilities, is the main task of a social educator. This direction of Science, which argues about the processes taking place in their minds, the influence of reality on people in our social life, is emerging today as a social order.

Hence the emergence of social pedagogy manifested itself on the basis of social necessity.

Social pedagogy and pedagogical sociology is a branch of pedagogical science that studies the laws of socialization of children and social education and social education of children. That is, upbringing is not just educational institutions, it has its own appearance in all aspects of the public, society as a whole.

Social pedagogy is a science that explains the thoughts, beliefs, ideas, views, feelings, various forms of behavior that are formed in people during the process of collaborative work activities in society. The main task of social pedagogy is to explain the pedagogical nature and laws of each individual's existence in society, the complex interactions that he establishes with individuals similar to him, observing social norms, and the employees formed by their influence.

Social pedagogy has a long and deep tradition both in Uzbekistan and in other countries of the world. Nevertheless, during the former Soviet regime, the achievements of social pedagogy were ignored. That is why Social Pedagogy as a new area includes not only the Departments of state and public bodies of socio-pedagogical specialists, but also a system that trains specialists, as well as a research base of socio-pedagogical activity.

After the formation of work on the accumulation of social pedagogical experience in practice in social pedagogical and youth living complexes, associations consisting of employees of different ages, the whip of schools with social institutions changed. On this basis, the process of Pedagogy of social interaction developed intensively. So, unlike the disciplines and educational institutions that are engaged in educational education, social pedagogy is associated with all the facets of our social life.

It is worth noting that the human factor is decisive in social development, especially the awareness, spirituality, ideology, ideological factors of young people. In particular, in higher and secondary special educational institutions, attention should be paid to the fact that the human personality (student-student and teacher) is a priority in the issue of the content, form, influence of Education. The pedagogical legality is that parental education, the influence of the teacher-teacher personality are decisive in the formation of the student-student personality as a harmonious person. That is why the formation of the personality of the future economist teacher as a harmonious person, as a spiritual mentor-specialist is a priority. In this regard, the acquisition of knowledge about the history of pedagogy is of great importance. In short, the main thing is that in higher educational institutions the knowledge taught from the history of the pedagogical direction is taught as universal and national values, it is in youth that national pride, national spirituality, love of the place where he was born and raised, education in the spirit of humanity.

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